

EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES OF INDIAN-ALMOND ORIGINATED SURFACTANT IN ENHANCED OIL RECOVERY APPLICATIONS

Harry Budiharjo Sulistyarso ^{a*}, Joko Pamungkas ^a, and Yulius Deddy Hermawan ^b
^{a*}Department of Petroleum Engineering, University of Pembangunan National "Veteran"
Yogyakarta, Sleman, 55283, Yogyakarta, Indonesia.
^bDepartment of Chemical Engineering, University of Pembangunan National "Veteran"
Yogyakarta, Sleman, 55283, Yogyakarta, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT

Chemical injection to enhance oil recovery is proven to increase oil recovery, but the use of chemicals can be environmentally damaging, so this research is very important as an effort to use natural chemicals as surfactants derived from Indian Almonds to reduce the environmental hazards caused. Surfactants from this natural material will be tested with the stages of aqueous stability, phase behavior, viscosity, density, interfacial tension, and core flooding. The results showed that the surfactant from Indian Almonds can be completely soluble with brine, forming a bottom-phase emulsion. The optimum interfacial tension value was obtained at 7.5% concentration of 6.5 mN/m; at this concentration, the critical micelle concentration was reached. Subsequently, the application of the core flooding test resulted in a significant increase in oil recovery, reaching 74.36% for artificial cores with a mesh size of 50 and 62.5% for artificial cores with a mesh size of 40. This study shows the surfactants from Indian Almonds has technical capabilities as the EOR method for the alternative chemical injection.

Keywords: coreflood, recovery factor, surfactants, indian-almond

INTRODUCTION

Enhanced oil recovery (EOR) is a technique to improve oil recovery (S. Hosseini et al., 2020). One of the EOR techniques is a chemical injection; according to (S. Hosseini et al., 2020), the chemical injection can reduce the value of interfacial tension (IFT) and rock wettability so that it can reduce capillary pressure and allow oil to be produced. Meanwhile, according to (Behrang et al., 2021), the focus of chemical injection is on decreasing the IFT value because this will affect the residual oil saturation value; if the IFT value decreases, the residual oil saturation value will also decrease so that the microscopic displacement efficiency will increase oil production. In addition, the primary mechanism expected from the chemical injection is to change the wettability of rock; according to (Golabi et al., 2012), wettability has a significant effect on increasing oil recovery because it has a direct impact on the distribution, location, and flow of oil and water in the reservoir during oil production.

When discussing chemical injection, there will be many techniques that can be used; the above is a general role of chemical injection; more specifically, one of the chemical injection techniques is chemical injection using surfactants. According to (S. N. Hosseini et al., 2015), surfactants can be classified as non-ionic, anionic, cationic, and zwitterionic groups. Surface-active agents are chemical substances that adsorb onto a surface or fluid interface at low concentrations in a system (Golabi et al., 2012). Apart from the function of the chemical injection above, surfactants have a role in forming an emulsion between oil and water and increasing the mobility of the oil (S. N. Hosseini et al., 2015).

Research has shown that surfactants can improve oil recovery, especially surfactants from manufactured chemicals. For example, a study by (Shabib-Asl et al., 2016) using a surfactant from Alpha Olefin Sulphonate (AOS), this surfactant is an anionic surfactant, the results show that AOS can reduce the IFT value of oil with a concentration of 1% wt at a salinity of 500 ppm by $10^{-1} \times 7$. Furthermore, research (Han et al., 2020) using surfactants of Alkyl benzene sulfonate (ABS) and Alpha olefin sulfonate (AOS) showed that the oil recovery after the core flooding test was up to the highest 93.9% with residual oil

saturation of 3.4%. Furthermore, in the study (Han et al., 2020), the materials used were surfactant foam and surfactant nanoparticle foam (denoted as surfactant NP foam), showing The surfactant-NP foam flooding has a better oil displacement effect and can enhance the recovery factor by more than 30%.

According to the above condition, are surfactants from natural chemicals from Indian-Almond able to work the same as the ingredients from the manufacturer components? Thus, through this study, the anionic surfactant ability of Indian Almind will be analyzed on the physical properties of the oil and improve the oil recovery.

BASIC THEORY

Indian-Almond

Based on (Nampoothiri et al., 2020), in their research state, the Terminalia catappa tree belongs to the family of leadwood trees growing in tropical areas like Asia, Africa, and Australia (Janick and Paull 2008). It is popularly known as the Indian almond, country almond, sea almond, Malabar almond, beach almond, tropical almond, and false kamani (Henn, McCoy, and Vaughan 2014; Kepler 1990). The tree grows to a height of up to 35 m with a symmetric crown and horizontal branches. The fruits of the T. Catappa tree are corky and look burble in color while fully ripe. Fruit contains an ample single seed that is tasty, like an almond. The ovoid leaves grow 15–25 cm long and 10–14 cm wide. The type of Indian Almond consists of about 200 species of trees and shrubs spread in tropical and sub-tropical areas worldwide (Raju, 2012). Meanwhile, what is known in Indonesia is Terminalia catappa. The number of seeds between 22 – 69 seeds/kg or an average of 40 ± 11 . Indian-Almond seed is one of the materials containing cellulose with the composition of lignocellulose in the shell of Indian-Almond seeds is 16.60% cellulose, 24.70% hemicellulose, and 43.46% lignin. The composition plays a significant role as an ingredient in making surfactants.

Lignin

Lignin is a natural, multichromatic ring macromolecular compound composed of hydrophobic nonpolar frameworks of phenyl propane and polar groups like carboxyl. Alkali lignin is a kind of anionic organic compound. It has a hydrophilic and a hydrophobic part (benzene ring, side chain), which has an anionic surfactant effect. When lignin is used as a surfactant because of its structure constraints, its surface activity and application performance are subject to certain restrictions. To improve the performance of lignin surfactant, researchers usually use hydroxymethylation, sulfonmethylation, alkylation, oxidation, amination, and carbonylation reaction to introduce hydrophilic and lipophilic groups into its molecular structure. It aims to prepare the salts of sodium, potassium, and ammonium, along with nonionic compounds. The modified lignin surfactant has good surface activity, adhesion, and complexation. Its industrial application is extensive. It can be used as an oil chemical additive, asphalt emulsifier, mud thinner, water treatment agent, dye dispersant, cement additive, and pesticide. Lignin has achieved large-scale applications with high added value and performance (Jin Huang et al. 2019; Xin L et al. 2008). The application of lignin and its derivatives in the industry is related mainly to its surface activity, including oil chemicals and concrete water reducers. Lignin compounds can be classified into cationic surfactants, anionic surfactants, amphoteric surfactants, and nonionic surfactants depending on the difference in the charge groups contained therein (jin Huang et al. 2019)

Chemical Injection

Chemical Flooding (Chemical Injection) is an advanced oil production method that adds chemicals to the injection water to increase oil recovery. EOR chemicals are polymers, alkalis, and surfactants. The injection of polymers with waterfloods increases the viscosity of the aqueous phase and, consequently, mobility as they move from the injection well toward the producer. Additionally, the polymer solution increases oil recovery by reducing permeability to water in the reservoir (Gbadamosi et al., 2019; Rafa et al., 2016). Surfactant solutions reduce the IFT between water and crude oil by reacting with certain constituents, thereby solubilizing interfacial films and causing emulsification (Gbadamosi et al., 2019; Cheraghian et al., 2016). The IFT reduction causes a lowering of the capillary forces of trapped and residual oil. Besides, surfactant adsorbs on reservoir rocks to change rock wettability, increasing oil

recovery. Alkali flooding operates with a mechanism similar to surfactant solutions, though with a different injectant (Gbadamosi et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2007). Foam flooding ensures the diversion of injected fluid from thief zones to low permeable regions of the reservoir (Gbadamosi et al., 2019; Bashir et al., 2018). Meanwhile, AP, AS, and ASP flooding are borne out of the basis to incorporate the different strengths and efficiency of alkali, surfactant, and polymer solutions to improve the pore scale and sweep efficiency of the Original Oil In Place (OOIP) (Gbadamosi et al., 2019; Mandal, 2015).

Surfactants

Surfactants are chemicals whose molecules always find a place between two fluids that do not want to mix, and surfactants bind the two fluids into an emulsion. The surfactant in the slug must be made to form a micelle, an active surfactant capable of binding water and oil at a specific concentration. The surfactant mixture is still monomeric if the concentration is still tiny. For this reason, each slug needs to know its CMC (Critical Micelles Concentration), a specific concentration, so that the surfactant mixture that was originally monomeric turns into micelles. The surfactant commonly used in the EOR exploitation process is Sodium Sulfonate which has a negative ionic charge. At the same time, other types are rarely used. The surfactant solution, commonly used in the field for pressing the residual oil resulting from the propulsion of water, consists of components of surfactant, water, oil, and alcohol as cosurfactants. This liquid surfactant mixture is injected into the reservoir as a slug and then driven by a polymer solution to improve flow mobility, followed by pushing water to save polymer materials. Slug, usually used from 5-15% PV, is expected to produce additional gains above the gain if used for secondary recovery.

METHODOLOGY

This research methodology was carried out by preparing tools and materials and collecting data to analyse the effect of surfactants on the total value of oil recovery.

3.1. Preparing the surfactant

The mechanism for making surfactants starts from the grinding stages, removing extractive substances, delignification, and sulfonating lignosulfonates. In this process, surfactant powder known to contain lignin is reacted with sodium bisulphite, and the pH is adjusted to 4 using sulfuric acid with the aim of delignification and sulfonation processes to form a sodium lignosulphonate solution.

3.2. Preparing Artificial Core

The artificial core is made using several compositions, including quartz sand with mesh sizes of 40 and mesh sizes of 50, with the compositions for quartz sand and cement being 70% and 30%, then mixed with sufficient water.

3.3 Aqueous Stability & Phase Behaviour Test

Aqueous stability is carried out to determine whether the surfactant is suitable for surfactant injection. If two phases are formed, the surfactant solution does not pass the aqueous stability test. Phase behaviour test is carried out to see the phase formed between Sodium Lignosulfonate (SLS) Olekimia surfactant with crude oil and formation water after contact. This test was conducted to determine the compatibility between Indian-Almond surfactants with crude oil and formation water.

3.4. Oil-Water Interfacial Tension (IFT) Test

The IFT test was conducted to determine the surfactant's ability to reduce the value of the interfacial tension between oil and brine. Crude oil and surfactant Indian- Almond samples were tested using a spinning drop tensiometer.

3.5. Density & Viscosity Test

Density measurements were carried out using a pycnometer and digital scale; this aims to determine the effect of increasing the density of the oil sample after adding surfactant and for input data on the viscosity test. Viscosity tests were carried out on crude oil samples before and after being added with

Indian-Almond surfactant at several concentrations. This stage aims to determine the effect of the sample's viscosity.

3.6. Core Flooding Test

The last stage of this research is the core flooding test using an artificial core that has met the screening criteria for permeability and porosity values to determine the oil recovery obtained, both before surfactant injection and after surfactant injection so that it can be seen the addition of oil obtained.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research was conducted at the laboratory enhanced oil recovery Universitas Pembangunan Nasional Veteran Yogyakarta. The test procedures that have been carried out include making Indian-almond surfactants, testing the compatibility of Indian-almond surfactants with brine, measuring the physical properties of crude oil after adding surfactants and measuring rock physical properties, including measuring porosity and permeability. Then test the increase in oil recovery through a core flooding test using an artificial sand core.

4.1 Indian-Almond

Fig. 1. Indian-Almond Preparation as Surfactant

Table 1. Characteristics of Sodium Lignosulfonate Indian-Almond Surfactants

Characteristics	Score
Color	Brownish-yellow
pH	5
Smell	Acid with sulfur
Solubility in water	Dissolved

Table 2. Indian-Almond Sodium Lignosulfonate Surfactant Content

Content	%
Lignosulfonates	80
Reducing sugar	7
Sulfur	6.6
Calcium	0.5
Sodium	7
Nitrogen	0.1

Based on the Figure 1 as a step to conduct the research, subsequently in the Table 2 as the result, the Indian almond surfactant has a pH of 5, brownish yellow, and blackish brown, indicating the presence of a -SO₃- group in the double-bond lignosulphonate structure. Then because the type of surfactant is sodium lignosulfonate (SLS), this surfactant has a slightly acidic smell; the addition of the -SO₃- group results in sulfur. This SLS surfactant from Indian Almond is also soluble in water, so it passes the compatibility

test. The general content of this SLS surfactant includes 80% Lignosulfonate, 7% Reducing Sugar, 6.6% Sulfur, 0.5% Calcium, and 0.1% Nitrogen

4.2. Artificial Core

The artificial core is a core sample that was made in the laboratory to replace the availability of the native field core, in which the physical properties of the artificial core were made to imitate the physical properties of the field core so that these artificial core samples can be used to represent the native field core in laboratory experiments. Artificial cores were made using several compositions, including quartz sand using mesh sizes 40 and 50. The compositions of quartz sand and cement were 70% and 30%, respectively, and then were blended with a proper amount of water.

Table 3. Permeability Measurement Result of Core Mesh

Sample Core	Viscosity cp	Permeability mD	Sample Core	Viscosity cP	Permeability mD
40-1	0.01884	122.2	50-1	0.01884	108.81
40-2	0.01884	124.1	50-2	0.01884	92.23
40-3	0.01884	114.4	50-3	0.01884	85.69
40-4	0.01884	115.6	50-4	0.01884	111.74
40-5	0.01884	122.6	50-5	0.01884	87.53
40-6	0.01884	122.4	50-6	0.01884	77.55
40-7	0.01884	129.1	50-7	0.01884	93.47
40-8	0.01884	110.1	50-8	0.01884	102.71
40-9	0.01884	116.7	50-9	0.01884	116.37
40-10	0.01884	126.1	50-10	0.01884	142.60

Based on these results, the porosity and permeability values used must be between 16-18%, considering the EOR screening criteria to perform optimally as a surfactant. The permeability measurement results can be seen in Table 3. So accordingly, the core samples to be used are core sample number 40-09 for mesh 40 and core sample number 50-02 for mesh 50.

4.3. Sample of Fluid

4.3.1. Brine

The formation water samples that are used in this study came from a field located in Wonocolo, Cepu, Central Java. These formation water samples were used in the Aqueous Stability Test, Interfacial Tension (IFT), Density Test, Phase Behavior, and core flooding tests. Subsequently, it will be used to determine the effect of the application of the Indian-Almond Surfactant to increase the oil recovery factor. Before the formation water is applied, the formation water is filtrated to remove impurities from the fields. The characteristics of the formation water are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Brine Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Salinity	8014 mg/L
pH	8

Based on the above, the ideal screening criteria for surfactant injection was brine with less than 200,000 ppm salinity. Hence, based on the field formation water characteristics, it was found that the brine has a salinity of 8014 mg/L (ppm). At this stage, we did not carry out a salinity test because this brine formed type 2 emulsion, which has reached the test standard as a surfactant for injection into artificial core according to the Special Task Force for Upstream Oil and Gas Business Activities of the Republic of Indonesia.

4.3.2. Crude Oil

Crude oil samples were obtained for this study from Wonocolo, Cepu, Central Java, which will be tested for density, viscosity, phase behavior, IFT, and core flooding. Subsequently, the effect of Indian Almond surfactant addition on the changes in physical properties and oil recovery factor will be analyzed. Before applying the sample, it was filtrated using Wattman No. 42 papers to eliminate impurity precipitates. The characteristics of the crude oil samples are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Crude Oil Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Density	0.903 gr/cc
SG	0.89
API	27 °API

Based on the table above, the characteristics of the types of crude oil samples that were used must be in line with the characteristics of the EOR screening criteria, regardless of the API value limitation that can be used for the surfactant injection process, which is $25 > \text{API}$. In contrast, the oil sample used was light-medium with an API value of 27.

4.3.3. Compactibility Test

Based on the Figure 2. It show from the aqueous stability test results, the surfactant was completely soluble with a clear or cloudy appearance. Surfactants that were completely soluble, clear, or cloudy, were surfactants that passed the aqueous stability test and proceeded to the subsequent tests.

Fig. 2. The results of the Aqueous Stability Test

4.4. Fluid Sample Test

4.4.1. Phase Behaviour Test

Fig. 3. Phase Behaviour Test Result

Table 6. Microemulsion Observation Results in Phase Behavior Test

Concentration	Time (Day)							
Surfactants	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2.50% (v/v)	0	0.015	0.05	0.075	0.1	0.15	0.15	0.15
5% (v/v)	0	0.025	0.075	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.2	0.2
7.50% (v/v)	0.025	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.25	0.25
10% (v/v)	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.3	0.3

Table 7. Observation Result of Microemulsion Type in Phase Behavior

Concentration	Volume	Microemulsion Type	Upper Brine Volume	Bottom Oil Volume	Microemulsion Volume
Surfactant	(ml)	-	(ml)	(ml)	(ml)
2.50% (v/v)	7	Bottom Phase (II-)	4.2	4.35	0.15
5% (v/v)	7	Bottom Phase (II-)	4	4.2	0.2
7.50% (v/v)	7	Bottom Phase (II-)	3.8	4.05	0.25
10% (v/v)	7	Bottom Phase (II-)	3.85	4.15	0.3

Fig. 4. Phase Behaviour Results

Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, it was found that in the phase behavior test, a lower phase emulsion was formed, which means an emulsion formed in the water phase (it can be seen in Figure 3.), in a two-phase condition, transparent (translucent clear), the microemulsion observed after observation for seven days. In line with research conducted by (Kwan Min Ko, 2014) at various concentrations carried out from a concentration of 0.5% (b / b) to 2.2% (b / b), subsequently based on Figure 4. the results showed an increase in emulsion viscosity with each concentration increase and at each concentration formed a different microemulsion Winsor type, based on the research found at a concentration of 2.2% which produced the highest concentration of Winsor type two, this is similar to this study, with each concentration increase, the thickness of the emulsion will increase until it reaches the CMC value, the thickness will be optimum, which means it will not increase anymore because the surfactant has reached its ideal state.

4.4.2. Interfacial Tension (IFT) Test Result

Fig. 5. Relationship of IFT to Treatment of Indian Almond Surfactant Concentration

Fig. 6. Determination of Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC)

Based on Figure 5, shows the value of IFT at various concentrations. After finding the IFT value at various concentrations, a graph was made to determine CMC, shown in Figure 6. The IFT value test was performed to determine the surfactant's ability to move oil in the rock pores. The lower the IFT value, the more efficiently the oil will flow. The results of observations on the spinning drop tensiometer were used to measure the IFT value dynamically (rotated). Based on the test, the lowest IFT value was found at a concentration of 7.5% at a temperature of 70 oC from the four concentration variations measured (2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10%) with an IFT value of 6.5 mN/m then after a concentration of 10% the IFT value increased to 9.1 mN/m. The concentration of 7.5% was used as the CMC value. Generally, the IFT values of non-treated oil and water were 35-35-36 mN/m. This result is relevant to the IFT measurement of the initial oil and water, where at 70 oC, the IFT was 32.78 mN/m; this result can be found in Figure 6. Until the CMC decreases the IFT value, it can be concluded that this Indian-Almond surfactant can be used as a chemical injection to increase further oil recovery. We agreed that the CMC value would no longer decrease the IFT value; it will tend to decrease and even increase; this is like research by (Kwan Min Ko, 2014), (Ossama Massarweh, et.al 2020; Kumar and Mandal, 2019) and (Ossama Massarweh, et.al 2020; Abbas et al., 2020).

4.4.3. Oil Density and Viscosity Test Result

Fig. 7. Density Measurement Results on the Treatment of Ketapang Surfactant Concentration

Fig. 8. Indian-Almond Surfactant Viscosity Relationship

Fig. 9. Viscosity Relationship Against Indian-Almond Surfactant Concentration Treatment

Based on the density measurement results, Figure 7 shows that the density of the oil sample would increase according to the addition of Indian-Almond surfactant concentration; this is caused by the Indian-Almond surfactant has a denser density compared to the oil sample, so that while blending it will increase the density value of the sample. The highest density was found at the highest concentration of 10%. Subsequently, the viscosity measurement found in Figure 8 has shown that the viscosity of the Indian-Almond surfactant is relatively constant concerning temperature change; this is to determine whether the Indian-almond surfactant keeps working optimally when there is a temperature change and based on the figure, it can be seen that the viscosity of the Indian-almond surfactant has a resistance to temperature increase, which means that at any temperature increase, it can still work effectively.

Furthermore, as seen in Figure 9, Indian almond surfactant can reduce the viscosity of the crude oil sample so that Indian almond surfactant can be applied in the EOR injection process. Subsequently, the surfactant value was measured at various concentrations beginning with 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10% concentrations and at each increase in temperature starting from 30 oC, 40 oC, 50 oC, 60 oC, and 70 oC.

4.5. Coreflood Test

4.5.1. Oil Saturation

Table 8. Oil Saturation Measurement Results

Core	Pore Volume cc	OOIP cc	Water Volume Left cc	Soi %	Swi %
40-09	2.41	1.95	0.46	81%	19%
50-02	1.64	1.2	0.44	73%	27%

Fig. 10. Core flooding Test Result Mesh 40

Fig. 11. Core flooding Test Result Mesh 50

As the last stage is core flooding test; in this stage, the first step is to apply oil saturation, where the oil in the core flood chamber is injected into the core holder through the injection line so the oil will replace the volume of formation water that is already contained in the core. In contrast, the core has previously been saturated with formation water, and the injection pressure gauge injection pressure reads up to 120 PSIG with an injection rate of 0.5 ml/min. Based on this process, the OOIP value obtained is the same as the volume of water stored in the tube of 1.95 cc and 1.2 cc for each core mesh number 40 and mesh number 50 with Soi 81% and 73% and Swi 19% and 27%, which can be shown in Table 8. OOIP is the total volume of crude oil in the pore volume of the artificial core. After that, waterflooding injection is carried out to determine the Recovery Factor (RF), and this stage is a secondary recovery stage, RF values of 51.28% for core mesh number 40 and 41.67% for core mesh number 50 are obtained with Saturation Water (Sw) values of 0.39 and 0.43 for each mesh number. The oil is considered non-producible at this stage, so the surfactant is injected and enters the tertiary recovery stage. In this process, the RF gain increased by 15.38% for core mesh number 40 and 12.5% for core mesh number 50 with Saturation Oil (So) of 0.27 and 0.34 for core mesh number and Sw of 0.73 and 0.66 for core mesh number, respectively, with injection PV of 0.17-0.25 and 0.24-0.3 with cumulative injection PV of 0.8 and 0.9.

The final stage is surfactant injection after the soaking time. The aim is to give the surfactant time to reduce the IFT value of oil, and the soaking time is performed for 24 hours, the time is chosen based on the results of research (Sulistyarso et al., 2020), where the soaking time is the ideal and optimum time because if the soaking time is too fast, the surfactant's ability is not optimal to reduce the IFT of oil, on the other hand, if it is too long, the surfactant will form an emulsion so that a slug occurs in the core and reduce the RF value gained. Based on the results of the study, RF after 24 hours soaking time increased by 7.69% and 8.33% for each core mesh number 40 and 50. In the research conducted by (Kwan Min ko, 2014) using surfactants and co-surfactants, the surfactant used was dodecyl alkyl sulfate for heavy oil and light oil, This surfactant is an industrial chemical surfactant in core flooding tests found that in surfactant without co-surfactant at 114 mD core permeability obtained RF of 65.4% and 72.4% at 116 mD core permeability, while when added co-surfactant got a total RF of 68.9% with 116 mD core permeability and 74.2% at 115 mD core permeability. This means that in the research using industrial chemicals only the RF produced reached the highest 74.2%, then in this research using natural chemicals from Indian almonds the total recovery factor was obtained at 74.36% on core mesh 40 with a permeability of 116 and 62.5% at a permeability of 92 mD. So, it is evident that natural chemical surfactants have great potential to replace industrial chemical surfactants even though in the future further improvement and development must be conducted.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research that has been done, it can be concluded as follows:

- 1) In the aqueous stability test surfactant passes the test with all concentrations showing soluble in water or formed a transparent one-phase blend. So, this shows the Indian almond surfactant solution has reached optimum conditions in brine salinity at a concentration of 8014 mg/L.
- 2) Surfactant Indian almond can change the physical properties of oil by reducing the viscosity and IFT values so it can increase the value of oil recovery factor (RF). It was found in the viscosity test that Indian Almond surfactant performs well at 10% concentration at 60°C where the % decrease in viscosity is relatively constant and at that concentration it can reduce the largest viscosity from 4.1 cp to 3.14 cp. Subsequently, Indian almond surfactant reacts with the oil and then reduces the viscosity so that the oil can flow more easily.
- 3) In the IFT test, it was found that at a concentration of 7.5% at 70 °C, the smallest IFT value of 6.5 mN/m was obtained from the non-treated IFT of 40.14 mN/m. Subsequently, at a concentration of 10%, the IFT value increased to 9.1 mN/m. It can be concluded at this value the CMC value of the surfactant has been reached. Therefore, a concentration of 7.5% is the optimum concentration which is subsequently used for surfactant injection concentration in the core flood test.

- 4) In the phase behavior test, a Winsor Type-II microemulsion was formed where after observation for 7 days a translucent emulsion was formed between the upper brine and bottom oil at all concentrations that had been made.
- 5) Based on the results of the core flood test, the OOIP oil saturation stage was obtained as much as the volume of water contained in the tube, namely 1.95 cc and 1.2 cc for each core flood test and 1.2 cc for each core mesh 40 and 50 with Soi of 81% and 73% and Swi of 19% and 27%.
- 6) At waterflooding injection, RF values of 51.28% and 41.67% were obtained for core mesh 40-50 with So values of 0.39 and 0.43 and Sw 0.61 and 0.57. At this stage the oil is considered unproductive so that surfactant is injected and enters the tertiary recovery stage.
- 7) The last stage is surfactant injection after soaking time. Soaking time is done for 24 hours. Based on the results of the research conducted, RF after soaking time of 24 hours increased by 7.69% and 8.33% for each core mesh 40 and 50 with So values of 0.21 and 0.27 and Sw of 0.79 and 0.73 with injection PV of 0.29 and 0.3 and cumulative injection PV of 0.9.
- 8) This study shows that surfactants from natural chemicals Indian Almond have the same ability as surfactants from industrial materials, this is a finding and comparison from previous studies that used industrial chemicals in their experiments.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Institute for Research and Community Service (LPPM) for funding this research.

DECLARATIONS

On behalf of all the co-authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Behrang, M., Hosseini, S., & Akhlaghi, N. (2021). Effect of pH on interfacial tension reduction of oil (Heavy acidic crude oil, resinous and asphaltenic synthetic oil)/low salinity solution prepared by chloride-based salts. *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*, 205(May), 108840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2021.108840>
2. Belhaj, A. F., Elraies, K. A., Mahmood, S. M., Zulkifli, N. N., Akbari, S., & Hussien, O. S. E. (2020). The effect of surfactant concentration, salinity, temperature, and pH on surfactant adsorption for chemical enhanced oil recovery: a review. *Journal of Petroleum Exploration and Production Technology*, 10(1), 125–137. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13202-019-0685-y>
3. Chemistry, L. (2019). Lignin Chemicals and Their Applications. In *Lignin Chemistry and Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-813941-7.00004-7>
4. Golabi, E., Azad, F. S., Ayatollahi, S. S., Hosseini, S. N., & Akhlaghi, N. (2012). Experimental study of wettability alteration of limestone rock from oil-wet to water-wet using various surfactants. *Society of Petroleum Engineers - SPE Heavy Oil Conference Canada 2012*, 1, 746–761. <https://doi.org/10.2118/157801-ms>
5. Han, X., Chen, Z., Zhang, G., & Yu, J. (2020). Surfactant-polymer flooding formulated with commercial surfactants and enhanced by negative salinity gradient. *Fuel*, 274(March), 117874. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2020.117874>
6. Hosseini, S. N., Shuker, M. T., Hosseini, Z., Joao Tomocene, T., Shabib-asl, A., & Sabet, M. (2015). The role of salinity and brine ions in interfacial tension reduction while using surfactant for enhanced oil recovery. *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, 9(9), 722–726. <https://doi.org/10.19026/rjaset.9.2617>
7. Hosseini, S. N., Shuker, M. T., Sabet, M., Zamani, A., Hosseini, Z., & Shabib-Asl, A. (2015). Brine Ions and Mechanism of Low Salinity Water Injection in Enhanced Oil Recovery: A Review. *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, 11(11), 1257–1264. <https://doi.org/10.19026/rjaset.11.2233>
8. Hosseini, S., Sabet, M., Zeinolabedini Hezave, A., A. Ayoub, M., & Elraies, K. A. (2020). Effect of combination of cationic surfactant and salts on wettability alteration of carbonate rock. *Energy*

- Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization and Environmental Effects, 00(00), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15567036.2020.1778141>
9. Jiangyuan, Z. H. N. G., et.al.(2015). Research overview of microblog analysis. *Journal of Hebei University of Science & Technology*, 36(1)
 10. Ko, K. M., Chon, B. H., Jang, S. B., & Jang, H. Y. (2014). Surfactant flooding characteristics of dodecyl alkyl sulfate for enhanced oil recovery. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, 20(1), 228–233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2013.03.043>
 11. Massarweh, O., & Abushaikha, A. S. (2020). The use of surfactants in enhanced oil recovery: A review of recent advances. *Energy Reports*, 6, 3150–3178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2020.11.009>
 12. Nampoothiri, E. N., Bensam Raj, J., Thanigaivelan, R., & Karuppasamy, R. (2022). Experimental Investigation on Mechanical and Biodegradation Properties of Indian Almond–Kenaf Fiber-Reinforced Hybrid Composites for Construction Applications. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 19(1), 292–302. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2020.1739592>
 13. Putra, B. P., & Kiono, B. F. T. (2021). Mengenal Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) Sebagai Solusi Meningkatkan Produksi Minyak Indonesia. *Jurnal Energi Baru Dan Terbarukan*, 2(2), 84–100. <https://doi.org/10.14710/jebt.2021.111152>
 14. Sabet, M., Hosseini, S. N., Zamani, A., Hosseini, Z., & Soleimani, H. (2016). Application of nanotechnology for enhanced oil recovery: A review. *Defect and Diffusion Forum*, 367, 149–156. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/DDF.367.149>
 15. Shabib-Asl, A., Ayoub, M. A., Elraies, K. A., Hosseini, S., & Hematpour, H. (2016). Investigation into the effects of crude oil on foam stability by using different low salinity water. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 9(35). <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/2016/v9i35/88111>
 16. Sulistyarso, H. B., Pamungkas, J., Rahayu, S., Widiyaningsih, I., & Kurnia, R. A. (2020). Application of bio-surfactants as an effort to enhanced oil recovery (EOR) in Kawengan oil field. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 2245(July). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0006935>
 17. Sulistyarso, H. B., Pamungkas, J., Widiyaningsih, I., & Wahyuningsih, T. (2020). Biosurfactant Injection of U-Champ on Heavy Oil Sample in Laboratory for Preliminary to Pilot Project. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, 9(4), 46–50. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.d4751.119420>
 18. Xu, Z., Li, B., Zhao, H., He, L., Liu, Z., Chen, D., Yang, H., & Li, Z. (2020). Investigation of the Effect of Nanoparticle-Stabilized Foam on EOR: Nitrogen Foam and Methane Foam. *ACS Omega*, 5(30), 19092–19103. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.0c02434>
 19. Zaker, S., Parvizi, R., Hosseini, S., & Ghaseminejad, E. (2020). Crude oil behavior during injection of solutions containing MgSO₄ in the presence and absence of CO₂. *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization and Environmental Effects*, 00(00), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15567036.2020.1783397>

